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Review article

Pregledni članak

LAWS AND DOCUMENTS RELEVANT TO THE EDUCATION OF SERBS IN THE REPUBLIC OF CROATIA

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Abstract

Following the signing of the Basic Agreement on the Region of Eastern Slavonia, Baranja, and Western Srymia, also known as the Erdut Agreement, and the completion of the peaceful reintegration of the region into the Republic of Croatia, the educational rights of members of the Serbian national minority have been regulated by the Constitution of the Republic of Croatia, declarations, the Constitutional Act on Human Rights and Freedoms and on the Rights of Ethnic and National Communities or Minorities in the Republic of Croatia, and various decisions. When schools in the aforementioned region were integrated into the school system of the Republic of Croatia, the educational rights of members of national minorities were further defined by other laws and regulations and, following the signing of the Stabilisation and Association Agreement with the European Union, by the Constitutional Act on the Rights of National Minorities, as well as by decisions and programmes relevant to education. This paper presents a theoretical analysis of the educational rights of minorities, primarily the Serbian national minority. It explores the right to use their own language and script, and the right to be educated in their mother tongue and script. The paper also examines the organization and delivery of education in schools or classes where instruction is conducted in the minority language, various educational models and schooling forms, admission conditions in educational institutions, curricula for upbringing and education in the language and script of national minorities containing components related to the identity of the national minority, the manner of maintaining pedagogical documentation and records, textbook translations, and many other rights. All of this is examined through available documents and existing laws.

Keywords: Constitution, laws, documents, Serbian national minority, education.

Introduction

This paper examines the educational rights of the Serbian national minority starting from the signing of the Basic Agreement on the Region of Eastern Slavonia, Baranja, and Western Sirmia on November 12, 1995. It follows the process of the peaceful reintegration of the aforementioned region into the Republic of Croatia, which was completed on January 13, 1997. This process was formally concluded with the Letter from the Croatian Government to the Security Council on the Completion of the Peaceful Reintegration of the Area under Transitional Administration into the Republic of Croatia. Its effects continue to the present day.

When schools in this region were integrated into the Croatian educational system, the educational rights of national minorities were further defined by the Constitution of the Republic of Croatia, the Constitutional Act on the Rights of National Minorities, other laws and regulations, decisions, and programs significant for education. Therefore, this paper examines the educational rights of the Serbian national minority using available documents and existing laws. This primarily concerns the preservation of national identity, namely the language, culture, history, and religion of national minorities. These rights include the use of their language and script, the right to be educated in their mother tongue and script, organizing and conducting education in dedicated classes or institutions, educational plans and programs for upbringing and education in the language and script of national minorities that include components related to the identity of the national minority, the manner of maintaining pedagogical documentation and records, textbook translations, and many other rights.

Theoretical Document Analysis

The study examined documents, legislation, and sub-legislative acts significant for the education of Serbs in the Republic of Croatia, which guarantee various rights to national minorities: the Constitution of the Republic of Croatia from 1990, the Constitutional Act on Human Rights and Freedoms and on the Rights of Ethnic and National Communities or Minorities in the Republic of Croatia from 1991, the Act on the Confirmation of the Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities from 1997, the Act on the Confirmation of the European Charter for Regional or Minority Languages from 1997, and the Act on Upbringing and Education in the Language and Script of National Minorities, which came into force on May 27, 2000. In March 2005, an Agreement was signed between the Republic of Croatia and Serbia and Montenegro on the Protection of the Rights of the Croatian minority in Serbia and Montenegro and the Serbian and Montenegrin Minority in the Republic of Croatia, as well as Operational Programs issued by the Government of the Republic of Croatia.

All examined documents, legislation, and sub-legislative acts outline the rights and freedoms guaranteed by the Republic of Croatia to its national minorities. Following the signing of the Erdut Agreement, the 1990 Constitution of the Republic of Croatia remained in force, guaranteeing national minorities equality with the majority population, freedom to express their national identity, the use of their own language and script, and cultural autonomy. Subsequently, the first Constitutional Act on Human Rights and Freedoms and on the Rights of Ethnic and National Communities or Minorities in the Republic of Croatia was adopted in December 1991, guaranteeing, among other things, the right of national minorities and communities to education in their language and script.

To further protect the existence of national minorities, in September 1997, the Croatian Parliament adopted the Decision on the Promulgation of the Act on the Confirmation of the

Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities. The section on education emphasizes the need to take measures to promote the culture, history, language, and religion of national minorities and the majority population. The House of Representatives of the Croatian Parliament also adopted, at its session on October 17, 1997, the Act on the Confirmation of the European Charter for Regional or Minority Languages, according to which the use of regional or minority languages is a fundamental and inalienable human right. Also, three years later, a new Act on Upbringing and Education in the Language and Script of National Minorities was enacted, coming into force on May 27, 2000. This Act guarantees national minorities in the Republic of Croatia a substantial number of varied and important educational rights, which were reaffirmed in the new Constitutional Act on the Rights of National Minorities that Croatia was required to enact upon joining the European Union. On December 13, 2002, the Croatian Parliament adopted the Decision on the Promulgation of the Constitutional Act on the Rights of National Minorities, ensuring particular rights for national minorities. With the aim of protecting, preserving, and developing national, cultural, linguistic, and religious identity, in March 2005, an Agreement was signed between the Republic of Croatia and Serbia and Montenegro on the protection of the rights of the Croatian minority in Serbia and Montenegro, and the Serbian and Montenegrin minorities in the Republic of Croatia. In the Agreement, the parties agreed on numerous issues concerning the preservation and development of minority education in the Republic of Serbia, the Republic of Croatia, and Montenegro.

Although the rights of national minorities in the Republic of Croatia comply with the democratic norms of the United Nations and the highest European standards, some issues important for the education of Serbs have remained unresolved for many years. For this reason, the Government of the Republic of Croatia adopts Programs aimed at enhancing and improving existing mechanisms for the protection of minority rights, introducing new measures, and implementing previously planned activities, as well as activities that were not carried out in accordance with the plans and operational programs from previous years.

Results

The 1990 Constitution provides that the Croatian language and Latin script are in official use in the Republic of Croatia, but in certain local units, under conditions prescribed by law, another language, as well as Cyrillic or another script, may be introduced into official use. Additionally, all members of national minorities in the Republic of Croatia are guaranteed equality, freedom to express their national affiliation, free use of their language and script, and cultural autonomy (Constitution of the Republic of Croatia, 1990).

The first Constitutional Act on Human Rights and Freedoms and on the Rights of Ethnic and National Communities or Minorities in the Republic of Croatia was adopted on December 4, 1991. This Act guaranteed national minorities and communities, among other things, the right to be educated in their language and script. It also states that members of all ethnic and national communities or minorities may freely use their language and script in private and public life, and that the upbringing and education of these communities or minorities are conducted in kindergartens and schools in their language and script, in accordance with tailored programs including content related to their history, culture, and knowledge. It also allows for the establishment of separate school institutions or dedicated classes with instruction in the language and script of the respective ethnic and national community or minority (Constitutional Act on Human Rights and Freedoms and on the Rights of Ethnic and National Communities or Minorities, 1991).

Several years later, on September 19, 1997, the House of Representatives of the Croatian Parliament adopted the Decision on the Promulgation of the Act on the Confirmation of the Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities. The section concerning education states the need to undertake measures in the field of education and research to promote the culture, history, language, and religion of their national minorities and the majority population; provide opportunities for teacher training and access to textbooks; facilitate contacts between students and teachers of different communities; and ensure equal accessibility of education for members of national minorities at all levels.

The text of the Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities was translated from English into Croatian (Decision on the Promulgation of the Act on Confirmation of the Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities, 1997).

Member states of the Council of Europe and other signatory states of the Framework Convention, aiming to achieve greater unity among their members and to ensure the realization of the ideals and principles of their common heritage, considered that one means to achieve this goal is to maintain and realize human rights and fundamental freedoms, and that it is important to protect the existence of national minorities within their territories, as this is significant for stability, democratic security, and peace in Europe. In addition to respecting ethnic, cultural, linguistic, and religious identity, in pluralistic and democratic societies, it is necessary to create conditions for minorities to express, preserve, and develop their identities, as tolerance and dialogue are essential for cultural diversity to enrich every society (Decision on the Promulgation of the Act on Confirmation of the Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities, 1997).

Determined to establish principles and obligations to be respected in order to ensure the effective protection of national minorities, as well as the rights and freedoms of their members, within the framework of the law and respecting the territorial integrity and national sovereignty of states, the parties agreed, in the section concerning education, that it is necessary to undertake measures in the field of education and research to promote the culture, history, language, and religion of their national minorities and the majority population; provide opportunities for teacher training and access to textbooks; facilitate contacts between students and teachers of different communities; and ensure equal accessibility of education for members of national minorities at all levels (Decision on the Promulgation of the Act on Confirmation of the Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities, 1997).

The European Charter for Regional or Minority Languages was adopted in Strasbourg on November 5, 1992. On October 17, 1997, the House of Representatives of the Croatian Parliament adopted the Act on the Confirmation of the European Charter for Regional or Minority Languages, which was ratified by then-President Dr. Franjo Tuđman on October 22, 1997. The Council of Europe adopted this Charter considering that the use of regional or minority languages is a fundamental and inalienable human right, and that through it, language is preserved from extinction, while also promoting European cultural heritage, tradition, multilingualism, diversity, and democracy (Decision on the Promulgation of the Act on Confirmation of the European Charter for Regional or Minority Languages, 1997).

The Act on Upbringing and Education in the Languages of National Minorities from June 17, 1979, was repealed when the Parliament adopted a new Act on Upbringing and Education in the Language and Script of National Minorities on May 11, 2000, which came into force on May 27, 2000. This Act contains 21 articles and guarantees national minorities in the Republic of Croatia various rights relating to upbringing and education: the right to use their own language and script and receive education in their mother tongue and script; the organization and implementation of education in dedicated schools or classes where instruction is conducted in the minority language; the opening of schools or classes with fewer students than schools where instruction is provided in

the Croatian language and script; different models and forms of education; bilingual signage of school names and inscriptions on seals; curricula for upbringing and education in the language and script of national minorities containing content related to the cultural and historical identity of the minority; conditions for enrolment in schools; mandatory learning of the Croatian language and Latin script; employment of teachers who are fully proficient in the language and script of the national minority; majority representation of minority members in the governing bodies of educational institutions providing instruction in the minority language; provision of the necessary number of advisors and school inspectors from the minority who are fully proficient in the minority language and script; training of teachers for instruction in the minority language and script; and translation and publication of textbooks in minority languages (Act on Upbringing and Education in the Language and Script of National Minorities, 2000).

Under the Stabilization and Association Agreement with the European Union, the Republic of Croatia was required to adopt a new constitutional act on the rights of national minorities. On December 13, 2002, the Croatian Parliament adopted the Decision on the Promulgation of the Constitutional Act on the Rights of National Minorities, thus establishing a normative framework for full protection of national minority rights (Implementation of the Constitutional Act on the Rights of National Minorities in the Republic of Croatia).

The Constitutional Act on the Rights of National Minorities guarantees specific rights to national minorities, including the use of their language and script in private, public, and official use; upbringing and education in the minority language and script; cultural and religious autonomy; protection against any activity that may threaten their existence; and many other rights and freedoms (Constitutional Act on the Rights of National Minorities, 2002).

According to the Constitutional Act on the Rights of National Minorities and in accordance with the Act on Upbringing and Education in the Language and Script of National Minorities, members of national minorities have the right to upbringing and education in their own language and script, from preschool age, in elementary and secondary schools, as well as at higher education institutions that train teachers and other educational professionals to provide education in the language and script used by national minorities.

Schools providing instruction in the language and script of national minorities may be organized for a smaller number of students than schools with instruction in the Croatian language and script, and such institutions employ teachers who themselves belong to the minority and who are fully proficient in the language and script in which instruction is delivered (Act on Upbringing and Education in the Language and Script of National Minorities, 2000).

The Act on the Confirmation of the Agreement between the Republic of Croatia and Serbia and Montenegro on the Protection of the Rights of the Croatian Minority in Serbia and Montenegro and the Serbian and Montenegrin Minorities in the Republic of Croatia, adopted by the Croatian Parliament at its session on March 18, 2005, was promulgated by the President of the Republic of Croatia on March 23, 2005. The parties agreed to ensure minority members the right to express, preserve, and develop their national, cultural, linguistic, and religious identity; the right to maintain and develop minority education; the right to be educated in the language and script of the minority; education of minority members in accordance with specific programs; learning content related to the cultural and historical identity of the national minority in institutions offering instruction in the language and script of national minorities; keeping pedagogical documentation in the minority language; employment of teachers belonging to national minorities at all levels and forms of education; participation of national minorities in the governance of educational institutions where instruction is conducted in the language and script of national minorities; exchange of educational experts, school curricula, textbooks, and other teaching materials; awarding of scholarships; participation in professional development seminars for minority teachers; as well as

promoting cooperation between schools and creating conditions for mutual visits of students and teachers (Act on the Confirmation of the Agreement between the Republic of Croatia and Serbia and Montenegro on the Protection of the Rights of the Croatian Minority in Serbia and Montenegro and the Serbian and Montenegrin Minorities in the Republic of Croatia, 2005).

In addition to the Constitution of the Republic of Croatia and other laws, the Government of the Republic of Croatia adopts Operational Programs to protect and improve the existing level of rights of all national minorities. These programs consist of two parts: the first part addresses all national minorities, while the second part is an operational program for each minority individually (Operational Programs, 2024-2028).

The majority of activities outlined in the Operational Programs have been successfully implemented; however, some issues important for the education of Serbs and other national minorities remain unresolved. These include the development of standardized curriculum supplements for the national group of subjects, which will include up to 30% content dedicated to the history and culture of the national minority; financing of specific textbooks or other teaching materials for schools operating under models A, B, and/or C; equipping schools with necessary methodological and didactic materials; procurement of textbooks and supplementary teaching aids from the home countries of national minorities; and the establishment of departments for the Serbian national minority at Faculties of Education in Zagreb and Osijek (Operational Programs, 2017-2020, 2021-2024, 2024-2028).

Discussion and Conclusion

Since the signing of the Erdut Agreement and the completion of the peaceful reintegration process of the region of Eastern Slavonia, Baranja, and Western Srymia into the Republic of Croatia, the educational rights of members of the Serbian national minority have been regulated by the Constitution, laws, declarations, agreements, regulations, and decisions. Based on available documents and existing legislation, this paper examines the educational rights of minorities, primarily the Serbian national minority. All rights granted to national minorities are consistent with United Nations principles and contemporary European democratic standards, as they provide comprehensive protection of the rights of national minority members. Thus, members of the Serbian national minority in the Republic of Croatia have the right to use their own language and script; the right to be educated in their mother tongue and script; the organization and conduct of education in dedicated schools or classes where instruction is delivered in the minority language; various models and forms of education; specific conditions for enrolment in educational institutions; curricula for the upbringing and education in the language and script of national minorities which include sections related to the cultural and historical identity of the national minority; bilingual maintenance of pedagogical documentation and records; translation of textbooks; and many other rights. Despite ongoing efforts, certain issues important for the education of Serbs have remained unresolved for many years. These include the unfinished development of standardized curricular supplements for the national group of subjects, which would include up to 30% content dedicated to the history and culture of the national minority; funding of specific textbooks or other teaching materials for schools following models A, B, and C; equipping schools with necessary methodological and didactic materials; procurement of textbooks and supplementary teaching materials from the home countries of the national minorities; and the establishment of departments for the Serbian national minority at Faculties of Education in Zagreb and Osijek. Nevertheless, the Government of the Republic of Croatia has adopted a Program for the time period from 2024 to 2028, which aims to improve and enhance existing mechanisms for protecting minority rights, introduce new activities,

and implement activities previously planned in Operational Programs but not carried out according to the plans and programs from prior years.

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ZAKONI I DOKUMENTI ZNAČAJNI ZA OBRAZOVANJE SRBA U REPUBLICI HRVATSKOJ

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Apstrakt

Nakon potpisivanja Osnovnog sporazuma o području Istočne Slavonije, Baranje i Zapadnog Srema, odnosno Erdutskog sporazuma i završetka procesa mirne reintegracije Područja u Republiku Hrvatsku, obrazovna prava pripadnika srpske nacionalne manjine regulisana su Ustavom Republike Hrvatske, deklaracijama, Ustavnim zakonom o ljudskim pravima i slobodama i o pravima etničkih i nacionalnih zajednica ili manjina u Republici Hrvatskoj i odlukama. Kada su škole sa navedenog područja integrisane u školski sistem Republike Hrvatske, obrazovna prava pripadnika nacionalnih manjina dodatno su definisana drugim zakonima i pravilnicima, a nakon potpisivanja Sporazuma o pridruživanju Republike Hrvatske Evropskoj uniji - Ustavnim zakonom o pravima nacionalnih manjina, odlukama i programima značajnim za obrazovanje. Kroz rad se teorijski analiziraju obrazovna prava manjina, pre svega srpske nacionalne manjine. Istražuje se njihovo pravo na upotrebu vlastitog jezika i pisma, pravo na obrazovanje na maternjem jeziku i pismu, organizovanje i izvođenje rada u posebnim školama ili odeljenjima u kojima se nastava izvodi na jeziku manjine, različiti modeli obrazovanja i oblici školovanja, uslovi upisa u školske ustanove, nastavni plan i program vaspitanja i obrazovanja na jeziku i pismu nacionalnih manjina koji sadrži deo koji je u vezi sa posebnosti nacionalne manjine, način vođenja pedagoške dokumentacije i isprava, prevodi udžbenika te mnoga druga prava. Sve to se izučava putem dostupnih dokumenata i postojećih zakona.

Ključne reči: Ustav, zakoni, dokumenti, srpska nacionalna manjina, obrazovanje

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